

Solvent effect on protonation equilibria of 2,3-dihydroxybenzoic acid and malonic acid

Belete Yilma Hirpaye and Gollapalli Nageswara Rao*

Department of Inorganic and Analytical Chemistry, School of Chemistry, Andhra University,
Visakhapatnam-530 003, Andhra Pradesh, India

E-mail : gollapallinr@yahoo.com

Manuscript received online 12 October 2012, accepted 01 November 2012

Abstract : The protonation constants of 2,3-dihydroxybenzoic acid and malonic acid at 303.0 ± 0.1 K and 0.16 mol dm^{-3} ionic strength in 0–60% v/v dioxan-water mixtures were determined by the pH-metric method using MINQUAD75 computer program. Selection of the best fit chemical model of the protonation equilibria is based on standard deviation in protonation constants and residual analysis using crystallographic *R*-factor and sum of squares of residuals in all mass balance equations. Linear variation of protonation constants with inverse of dielectric constants of the solvent mixture has been attributed to the dominance of the electrostatic forces. Distributions of species, protonation equilibria and effect of influential parameters on the protonation constants have also been discussed.

Keywords : 2,3-Dihydroxybenzoic acid, malonic acid, protonation constants, dioxan, MINQUAD75.

Introduction

2,3-Dihydroxybenzoic acid (2,3-DHBA) is a monocatechol siderophore, isolated from *B. abortus* in cattle. It serves as nontoxic and effective chelating agent for ions with high charge to ionic radius ratio in the chelation therapy^{1,2}. It is involved in basic neurotransmitter metabolite, take part in glucose metabolism³ and in trace elements uptake by microorganisms⁴. It find extensive application for the preparation and study of polymeric complexes, which can serve as models for the interactions of metal ions with soil humic and fulvic organic matter⁵. It's redox multiplicity and antioxidant capability is of great interest for bioinorganic chemistry⁶. 2,3-DHBA is used as an anti-tumor agent^{7,8} which is active against melanoma cells. The ligand exhibited reduction of the inflammatory response in experimental phacoanaphylactic endophthalmitis, thus being an effective antiflogistic agent⁹. It has also been proposed as a marker of *in vivo* oxidative stress¹⁰. Enzymes such as 2,3-dihydroxybenzoate dehydrogenase or ligase catalyze the production or activation of 2,3-DHBA^{11,12}. 2,3-DHBA contains bidentate catechol part and one carboxylate oxygen atom that is either *ortho* or *meta* to phenol group of triprotic acid (H_3L) but they acts as salicylate type or catechol type and/or mixed

salicylate-catecholate type ligand^{13,14}. Malonic acid (MA) or propanedioic acid is a three-carbon dicarboxylic acid. The ionized form of malonic acid, as well as its esters and salts, are known as malonates¹⁵. MA can be metabolized to acetyl coenzyme A and that it is involved in fatty acid, aromatic, and mevalonate syntheses^{16,17}. It is important intermediates in synthesis of vitamins B₁ and B₆, barbiturates, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory agents, other numerous pharmaceuticals, agrochemicals, flavors and fragrance compounds¹⁸. Malonate is an inhibitor of cellular respiration; it binds to the active site of the succinate dehydrogenase in the citric acid cycle but does not react, thereby competing with succinate. For the oxidative phosphorylation reaction, malonate is an inhibitor for complex II, which again contains succinate dehydrogenase^{19,20}. Mixed solvents have been employed in different fields including pharmaceutical and analytical sciences. The knowledge of dielectric constant of mixed solvents is required to predict the drug's solubility and chemical stability in a water-cosolvent mixture and the analyte behavior in analytical methods²¹. Drug solubility in mixed solvents²² acid dissociation constants of drugs²³ and chemical stability of pharmaceuticals²⁴ could be explained considering dielectric constant of the solvent sys-

tem. So far no systematic report has appeared dealing with mixed solvent of dioxan-water mixture of various concentrations on 2,3-DHBA and MA. Hence, in this paper we present the effect of dielectric constant of the medium on the protonation equilibria of 2,3-DHBA and MA. Further, the various species detected in the present study and its concentration will be extrapolated to the biological system under similar conditions.

Results and discussion

Protonation equilibria :

The analysis of alkalimetric titration data of 2,3-DHBA and MA in dioxan-water mixture (0.0–60.0% v/v) shows that the acido-basic equilibria are active in the pH range 1.7–11.5 and 1.7–7.0, respectively. The protonation constants along with statistical parameters are given in Table 1. The protonation constants of 2,3-DHBA^{25–27} and MA^{28,29} in the aqueous medium are compared with data found in literature and they are in close agreement with the present values. A very low standard deviation in log β values indicates the precision of the parameters. The small values of U_{corr} (sum of squares of deviations in concentrations of ligand and hydrogen ion at all experimental points corrected for degrees of freedom) indicate

that the model can present the experimental data. The Kurtosis values indicate that the residual form leptokurtic pattern. The values of Skewness between –0.09 and 0.59 for 2,3-DHBA and –0.52 and 1.31 for MA evidence that the residual of many systems form a part of normal distribution; hence, least squares method can be applied to the present data. The efficiency of the model is further evident from the low crystallographic R values. The fitness of the model was tested by comparing the experimental titration data points and the theoretical curve (simulated) calculated from the values of acid dissociation constants of the ligands. The overlap of the typical experimental and simulated titrations data given in Fig. 1 indicates that the proposed models represent the experimental data.

Secondary formation function :

Secondary formation functions like average number of protons bound per mole of ligand (\bar{n}_H) and number of moles of alkali consumed per mole of ligand (a) are useful to detect the number of equilibria. Plots of \bar{n}_H versus pH for different concentrations of the ligand should overlap if there is no formation of polymeric species. Overlapping formation curves for 2,3-DHBA and MA (Fig. 2) rule out the polymerization of the ligand molecules.

Table 1. Best-fit chemical models of protonation equilibria of 2,3-DHBA and MA in dioxan-water mixtures

% v/v Dioxan	log β_1 (SD) ^a	log β_2 (SD)	NP	U_{corr}	Skewness	Kurtosis	χ^2	R -factor	pH-Range
2,3-DHBA									
0.0	10.11(1)	12.99(2)	84	3.229	0.26	3.86	16.95	0.0109	2.00–10.50
10.0	10.41(1)	13.39(1)	80	1.895	–0.09	3.83	6.40	0.0080	2.00–10.50
20.0	10.92(2)	14.21(3)	56	6.609	–0.02	3.04	11.86	0.0184	2.45–11.00
30.0	11.32(3)	14.87(4)	55	4.490	–0.05	4.10	4.04	0.0144	2.40–11.00
40.0	12.07(8)	15.98(9)	55	6.796	0.07	3.81	4.62	0.0172	2.40–11.30
50.0	12.53(19)	16.63(19)	63	1.331	0.14	2.11	9.75	0.0059	1.99–9.88
60.0	13.19(16)	17.63(16)	60	0.927	0.59	2.89	3.47	0.0049	1.99–9.89
MA									
0.0	5.39(1)	8.10(1)	112	1.615	–0.52	3.39	10.64	0.0068	1.80–8.00
10.0	5.64(1)	8.54(2)	95	1.310	1.31	5.49	16.23	0.0096	1.95–7.00
20.0	5.85(1)	8.84(2)	116	2.715	–0.50	5.26	12.83	0.0085	1.80–8.00
30.0	6.22(1)	9.41(2)	84	2.805	–0.97	5.83	15.81	0.0110	2.10–8.00
40.0	6.66(2)	10.20(3)	92	8.605	0.04	3.42	10.59	0.0157	1.90–7.00
50.0	6.89(1)	10.52(2)	92	2.044	–0.08	2.95	6.00	0.0077	1.90–7.00
60.0	7.29(1)	11.25(2)	96	2.340	–0.04	3.00	4.17	0.0077	1.80–7.00

$U_{\text{corr}} = UI(NP - m) \times 10^8$; NP = Number of points; m = number of protonation constants; SD = standard deviation; (a) $\log \beta_1 = \log K_2$, $\log K_1 = \log \beta_2 - \log \beta_1$; β and K are the overall and stepwise stability constants, respectively.

Fig. 1. Simulated (O) and experimental (solid line) alkalimetric titration curves in 20% v/v dioxan-water mixture : (A) 2,3-DHBA and (B) MA; (a) 0.25, (b) 0.375 and (c) 0.50 mmol.

Fig. 2. Plot of (\bar{n}_H) versus pH in 20% v/v dioxan-water mixtures : (A) 2,3-DHBA and (B) MA; (\square) 0.25, (\circ) 0.375 and (Δ) 0.50 mmol.

It has shown in Fig. 2 the pH values at half integral values of \bar{n}_H correspond to the protonation constants of the ligands³⁰. Two half integrals value (0.5, 1.5) in the both of 2,3-DHBA and MA clearly show the presence of two protonation-deprotonation equilibria in the pH range of present study. The number of plateaus in the formation curves corresponds to the number of these equilibria. The maximum value of \bar{n}_H is two, which clearly infers that both ligands have two bound protons.

The plots of α versus pH are given in Fig. 3. The negative values of α correspond to the number of moles of free acid present in the titrand and the number of associable protons. The positive values indicate the number of dissociable protons in the ligand molecules. The maximum value of α in Fig. 3A is two, which indicates that 2,3-DHBA has two dissociable (carboxyl and phenolic) proton under the present investigation. The corresponding value for MA (Fig. 3B) is also 2, which emphasis that MA has two dissociable (two carboxyl) protons.

2,3-DHBA (H_3L) has three potential coordination centers (COO^- , O^- and O^-)^{8,25} with three protonation constants. The first proton (2-OH position in 2,3-DHBA) has a very high affinity for the L^{3-} ion and does not dissociate until pH ~ 13 , due to strong intramolecular hydrogen bond between carboxylate (COO^-) and phenol (OH) group^{26,31-33}. The next two protons coordinate to the other phenolate oxygen and carboxylate oxygen with log K value of 10.11 and 2.88, respectively.

Effect of systematic errors in best fit model :

The results of a study on the effect of systematic errors in the concentrations of ingredients and electrode calibration on the magnitude of protonation constants are given in Table 2 for a typical system. The order of ingredients that influences the magnitude of protonation constants due to incorporation of errors is alkali > acid >

Fig. 3. Plot of a versus pH in 20% v/v dioxan-water mixture; (A) 2,3-DHBA and (B) MA; (\square) 0.25, (\circ) 0.375 and (Δ) 0.50 mmol.

ligand > correction factor as was observed in the earlier studies³⁴. Increase in the standard deviations of $\log \beta$ upon incorporation of errors indicates that the experimental data have minimum errors.

Effect of solvent :

The reaction medium is one of the most important influencing factors in determining the equilibrium constants. It has been stated that up to an approximately 60% organic solvent concentration in dioxan-water mixtures the electrostatic effect predominates and $\log K$ of a ligands varies almost linearly with the reciprocal of the dielectric constant^{35,36}. Born's classical treatment holds good in accounting for the electrostatic contribution to the free energy change. According to this treatment, the energy of electrostatic interaction is related to dielectric constant. Hence, the $\log K$ values should vary linearly as a function of the reciprocal of the dielectric constant of the medium^{37,38}, which is observed in the present study (Fig. 4). Upon addition of dioxan more water molecules are replaced by organic molecules.

As the basicity of dioxan is lower than that of water, this non-electrostatic effect seems to decrease the proton-accepting property of the mixed solvent, as a whole; however, dioxan molecules progressively break down the H-bonded structure of water and this second non-electrostatic effect counteracts the first one, with respect to the proton acceptance property of the media. These considerations have been reflected³⁶ in the deviation from linearity of $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ plotted against $1/D$ in Fig. 4. This study is helpful to understand the co-solvent effect

Table 2. Effect of errors in influential parameters on protonation constants in 20% v/v dioxan-water mixture

Ingredient	%Error	$\log \beta_{mlh}$ (SD)			
		2,3-DHBA		MA	
		$\log \beta_1$ (SD)	$\log \beta_2$ (SD)	$\log \beta_1$ (SD)	$\log \beta_2$ (SD)
Alkali	0	10.92(2)	14.21(3)	5.85(1)	8.84(2)
	-5	11.42(9)	15.05(11)	6.40(4)	9.87(6)
	-2	11.09(4)	14.51(5)	6.06(2)	9.22(3)
	+2	10.77(2)	13.93(2)	5.64(1)	8.48(2)
	+5	10.54(2)	13.53(3)	5.33(3)	7.95(4)
Acid	-5	10.68(2)	13.69(3)	5.49(2)	8.07(3)
	-2	10.82(2)	14.00(3)	5.71(1)	8.53(2)
	+2	11.03(3)	14.43(4)	5.99(2)	9.15(3)
	+5	11.20(5)	14.78(7)	6.21(4)	9.65(6)

Table-2 (contd.)

Ligand	-5	10.78(2)	14.01(3)	5.68(1)	8.62(2)
	-2	10.87(2)	14.13(3)	5.78(1)	8.75(2)
	+2	10.98(3)	14.29(4)	5.91(1)	8.92(2)
	+5	11.07(3)	14.40(4)	6.00(2)	9.04(2)
log F	-5	10.93(2)	14.22(3)	5.85(1)	8.85(2)
	-2	10.92(2)	14.21(3)	5.85(1)	8.84(2)
	+2	10.92(2)	14.20(3)	5.85(1)	8.83(2)
	+5	10.92(2)	14.20(3)	5.84(1)	8.83(2)
Volume	-5	10.92(2)	14.21(3)	5.85(2)	8.89(3)
	-2	10.92(2)	14.21(3)	5.85(1)	8.86(2)
	+2	10.93(2)	14.20(3)	5.85(1)	8.82(2)
	+5	10.93(2)	14.20(3)	5.85(1)	8.78(2)

Fig. 4. Variation of step-wise protonation constant ($\log K$) with reciprocal of dielectric constant ($1/D$) of dioxan-water mixture : (A) 2,3-DHBA and (B) MA; (■) $\log K_1$ and (●) $\log K_2$.

at a molecular level³⁹⁻⁴¹ and provide useful information in aiding in the rational drug design, medicinal chemistry, biochemistry and molecular biology.

Distribution diagrams :

The best fit model (Table 1) was used to plot the distribution diagram (Fig. 5) of 2,3-DHBA and MA. The distribution diagram reveals that the presence of LH_2 ,

Fig. 5. Formation functions (O) and species distribution diagrams of (A) 2,3-DHBA and (B) MA in 20% v/v dioxan-water mixtures.

Fig. 6. Protonation-deprotonation equilibria of (A) 2,3-DHBA and (B) MA.

LH^- and L^{2-} in the case of 2,3-DHBA and LH_2 , LH^- and L^{2-} in the case of MA. The corresponding protonation and deprotonation equilibria and the pH ranges of existence of the species are shown in Fig. 6. In the pH range of study, 2,3-DHBA loses carboxylic and (*meta*) phenolic protons, successively.

Similarly, LH_2 species of MA is predominant at low pH. As the pH increases its concentration decreases exponentially and become almost zero at around pH 4. The LH^- species attains maximum concentration (92%) at around pH 4. The free ligand (L^{2-}) concentration progressively increases and attains the maximum (99%) at higher pH value. This conclusion is useful in predicting the possible metal-ligand complexes at a given pH.

Conclusions :

This work describes the effect of dielectric constant of the medium on the protonation constants of 2,3-DHBA and MA. The number of protonation-deprotonation equilibria has been predicted from the secondary functions. The change in the magnitude of protonation constants with co-solvent content indicates the influence of dielectric constant of the medium. The log values of protonation constants of 2,3-DHBA and MA linearly increase with decreasing dielectric constant of dioxan-water mixtures. This indicates the dominance of electrostatic forces

in the protonation-deprotonation equilibria. Introduction of errors in the influential parameters shows that the errors in the concentrations of alkali and mineral acid affect the protonation constants more than that of the ligand which also supports the appropriateness of the experimental conditions. Furthermore, the results obtained in this study should contribute to furthering our understanding of the acid-base behavior of substances in the widely used dioxan-water mixtures and of the chemical factors which are involved in more complicated biological process.

Experimental

Materials :

All the ligands used in this study are of analytical-grade purity. They were used as received. Stock solutions (0.05 mol L^{-1}) of 2,3-DHBA (Sigma-Aldrich) and MA (Himedia) were prepared in triple-distilled water by maintaining 0.05 mol L^{-1} hydrochloric acid concentration to increase the solubility. Dioxan was obtained from Merck, India, and used as received. Hydrochloric acid (Merck, India) of 0.2 mol L^{-1} was prepared. Sodium chloride (Merck, India) of 2 mol L^{-1} was prepared to maintain the ionic strength in the titrand. Sodium hydroxide of 0.4 mol L^{-1} was prepared. All the solutions

were standardized by standard methods. The errors in the concentrations of ligand and alkali were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) by the computer program COSWT (concentration of solution by weight method)⁴². The strengths of carbonate free alkali and mineral acid were checked by means of Gran plot method⁴³.

Alkalimetric titrations :

Alkalimetric titrations were carried out in media containing varying compositions of dioxan (0–60% v/v) maintaining an ionic strength of 0.16 mol L⁻¹ with sodium chloride thermostated at 303.0 ± 0.1 K an Elico LI-120 pH meter (readability 0.01) was used. The pH metric titration assembly consisted of a double walled spoutless pyrex glass vessel of 100 ml capacity fitted with a perspex lid through which the glass combination pH electrode, gas inlet-outlet tubes and burette tip were admitted. The titrand in the titration vessel was maintained inert by bubbling dried and pure nitrogen gas throughout the course of the titration to purge carbon dioxide and oxygen. Temperature was maintained by regular circulation of water from the thermostat bath. Potassium hydrogen phthalate (0.05 mol L⁻¹) and borax (0.01 mol L⁻¹) solutions were used to calibrate the pH meter. In each titration, the titrand consisted of approximately 1 mmol of hydrochloric acid in a total volume of 50 ml. The concentrations of 2,3-DHBA and MA in the titrands ranged between 0.25–0.50 mmols. The glass electrode was equilibrated in a well stirred dioxan-water mixture containing inert electrolyte for a week. At regular intervals strong acid was titrated against alkali to check the complete equilibration of the glass electrode. The calomel electrode was refilled with dioxan-water mixture of equivalent composition as that of the titrand. The details of experimental procedure and titration assembly have been detailed elsewhere⁴⁴. Typical alkalimetric titration curves are given in Fig. 1.

Modeling strategy :

The correction factor to be applied to pH meter dial reading was calculated with the computer program SCPHD⁴⁵. The best fit chemical model for each system investigated was arrived at using non-linear least-squares computer program, MINQUAD75⁴⁶, which exploits the advantage of constrained least-squares method in the initial refinement and reliable convergence of Marquardt algorithm. The reliability of the protonation constants were

verified from the statistical parameters and by introducing errors in the concentrations of the ingredients. The variation of stepwise protonation constants (log *K*) with the dielectric constant of the medium was analyzed on electrostatic grounds for the solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions.

Acknowledgement

BYH acknowledges the Indian Council for Cultural Relations (ICCR), New Delhi, for financial support.

References

1. B. H. Bellaire, P. H. Elzer, C. L. Baldwin and R. M. Roop, *Infect. Immun.*, 2003, **71**, 2927.
2. R. C. Scarrow and K. N. Raymond, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1998, **27**, 4140.
3. C. Pierpont and R. Buchanan, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1981, **38**, 45.
4. C. Bianchini, P. Frediani, F. Laschi, A. Meli, F. Vizza and E. Zianello, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1990, **29**, 3402.
5. A. Lymberopoulou-Karaliota, D. Hatzipanayioti, M. Kamariotaki, M. Potamianou, C. Litos and V. Aletras, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2005, **358**, 2975.
6. V. Aletras, A. Karaliota, M. Kamariotaki, D. Hatzipanayioti and N. Hadjiliadis, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2001, **312**, 151.
7. C. A. Tyson, S. E. Levalley, R. Chan, P. D. Hobbs and M. I. Dawson, *J. Pharmacol. Exp. Ther.*, 1984, **228**, 676.
8. V. P. Kotsaki-Kovatsi, A. J. Vafiadou, G. Koehler-Samuilidou and A. Kovatsis, *Vet. Hum. Toxicol.*, 1997, **39**, 211.
9. E. P. Kable and P. G. Parsons, *Biochem. Pharmacol.*, 1988, **37**, 1711.
10. A. Ghiselli, O. Laurenti, G. De Mattia, G. Maiani and A. F. Luzzi, *Free Rad. Biol. Med.*, 1992, **13**, 621.
11. A. Sakaitani, F. Rusnak, N. R. Quinn, T. B. Frigo, G. A. Berctold and C. T. Walsh, *Biochem.*, 1990, **29**, 6789.
12. F. Rusnak, W. S. Fataci and C. T. Walsh, *Biochem.*, 1989, **28**, 6827.
13. E. Mentasti, E. Pelizzetti and G. Saini, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1976, **38**, 785.
14. C. Gerard, R. Njomgang, J. Pierrard, J. Rimbault and R. P. Hugel, *J. Chem. Res.*, 1987, **1987**, 294.
15. K. Yu Sam, *J. Biochem. Mol. Biol.*, 2002, **35**, 443.
16. J. de Vellis, L. M. Shannon and J. Y. Lew, *Plant Physiol.*, 1963, **38**, 686.
17. D. K. Stumpf and R. H. Burris, *Plant Physiol.*, 1981, **68**, 992.
18. O. F. Goulart and H.-Y. Schafer, *J. Braz. Chem. Soc.*, 1999, **10**, 235.

19. D. V. Dervartanian and C. Veeger, *Biochim. Biophys. Acta*, 1964, **92**, 233.
20. D. L. Nelson and M. M. Cox, "Lehninger Principles of Biochemistry", 4th ed., W. H. Freeman, New York, 2005.
21. J. Abolghasem, S. Shahla and C. Hak-Kim, *Int. J. Pharm.*, 2004, **269**, 353.
22. D. Dumanovic, D. J. Kosanovic, D. Ardakovic and J. Jovanovic, *Pharmazie*, 1992, **47**, 603.
23. D. W. Newton, W. J. Murray and M. W. Lovell, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1982, **71**, 1363.
24. S. Sanyude, R. A. Locock and L. A. Pagliaro, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1991, **80**, 674.
25. R. Aydin and V. Ozer, *Tr. J. Chem.*, 1997, **21**, 428.
26. T. Kiss and H. Kozlowski, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1989, **20**, 49.
27. S. K. Sahoo, R. K. Bera, M. Baral and B. K. Kanungo, *Acta Chim. Slov.*, 2008, **55**, 243.
28. J. Briucal, V. Lubes, M. Lorena and F. Brito, *J. Chil. Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **4**, 285.
29. B. B. V. Sailaja, T. Kebede, G. N. Rao and M. S. P. Rao, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **79**, 155.
30. A. B. Naik and M. Narwade, *American-Eurasian J. Sci. Res.*, 2008, **3**, 212.
31. N. Turkel, M. Berker and U. Oze, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 2004, **52**, 929.
32. L. J. Lajune, R. Portanova, J. Piispanen and M. Tolazzi, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1997, **69**, 329.
33. B. Y. Hirpaye, M. T. Zekarias and G. N. Rao, *Chem. Speciation. Bioavail.*, 2012, **24**, 1.
34. K. V. S. Devi, B. R. Raju and G. N. Rao, *Acta Chim. Slov.*, 2010, **57**, 398.
35. K. Sarkar and B. S. Garg, *J. Chem. Sci.*, 1986, **97**, 133.
36. S. Arzik, E. M. Ayan and A. Sedat, *Turk. J. Chem.*, 2008, **32**, 721.
37. M. T. Beck and I. Nagypal, "Chemistry of Complex Equilibria", Ellis Horwood Limited, New York, 1990.
38. M. Born, *Z. Phys.*, 1920, **1**, 45.
39. Y. Obata, K. Takayama, Y. Maitani and Y. Machida, *Int. J. Pharm.*, 1993, **89**, 191.
40. K. Takahashi, S. Tamagawa, T. Katagi, H. Yoshitomi, A. Kamada, J. H. Rytting, T. Nishihata and N. Mizuno, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1991, **39**, 154.
41. S. Gungor and N. Bergisadi, *Pharmazie*, 2004, **59**, 39.
42. R. S. Rao and G. N. Rao, "Computer Applications in Chemistry", Himalaya Publishing House, Mumbai, 2005.
43. G. Gran, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1988, **206**, 111.
44. M. P. Latha, V. M. Rao, T. S. Rao and G. N. Rao, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Ethiop.*, 2007, **21**, 363.
45. M. R. Vegi, PhD thesis, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam, India, 2006.
46. P. Gans, A. Sabatini and A. Vacca, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1976, **18**, 237.